

POWER SYSTEM HARMONIC EXTRACTION USING DSP TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the extraction of power system harmonics using digital signal processing (DSP) techniques. Harmonics are integral multiples of a fundamental frequency and result from non-linear electrical loads, affecting voltage and current waveforms. The study explores how harmonics are periodic and how DSP methods are applied to analyze and mitigate their impact on power systems. The importance of understanding harmonic behavior for maintaining power quality is emphasized.

Keywords: Harmonics, DSP Technique, Power Systems, Non-Linear Loads

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1. INTRODUCTION

A harmonic of a wave is a component frequency of the signal that is an integer multiple of the fundamental frequency, i.e. if the fundamental frequency is f , the harmonics have frequencies $2f, 3f, 4f, \dots$ etc. The harmonics have the property that they are all periodic at the fundamental frequency, therefore the sum of harmonics is also periodic at that frequency. As multiples of the fundamental frequency, successive harmonics can be found by repeatedly adding the fundamental frequency. For example, if the fundamental frequency (first harmonic) is 25 Hz, the frequencies of the next harmonics are: 50 Hz (2nd harmonic), 75 Hz (3rd harmonic), 100 Hz (4th harmonic) etc.

Harmonics (in power system) are a steady state components where the waveform to be analysed is assumed to be periodic. Harmonic voltages and currents in an electric power system are a result of non-linear electric loads.

A. Types of Harmonics

There are two types of harmonics:-

1. Current harmonics:- In a normal alternating current power system, the current varies sinusoidally at a specific frequency, usually 50 or 60 hertz. When a linear electrical load is connected to the system, it draws a sinusoidal current at the same frequency as the voltage (though usually not in phase with the voltage).

Current harmonics are caused by non-linear loads. When a non-linear load, such as a rectifier, is connected to the system, it draws a current that is not necessarily sinusoidal. The current waveform can become quite complex, depending on the type of load and its interaction with other components of the system. Examples of non-linear loads include common office equipment such as computers and printers, Fluorescent lighting, battery chargers and also variable-speed drives.

2. Voltage harmonics:- Voltage harmonics are mostly caused by current harmonics. The voltage provided by the voltage source will be distorted by current harmonics due to source impedance. If the source impedance of the voltage source is small, current harmonics will cause only small voltage harmonics.

B. Need to Analyse Harmonics

Harmonic frequencies in the power grid are a frequent cause of power quality problems. Harmonics degrades the performance of power system. Some of the disadvantages of harmonics in the power distributed network are listed below:

- a) The harmonics flowing in the distribution network downgrade the quality of the electrical power supply. There can have several negative effects on the operation of the power system
- b) Increased losses on the distribution system due to increase in the effective rms current
- c) Over-load in neutral conductors due to cumulative increase in the third harmonics created by the single phase loads
- d) Overloads, vibration and premature ageing of the generators, transformers and motors as well as increase in the noise level
- e) Overloads and premature ageing of the power factor correction capacitors
- f) Distortion of the supply voltage that can disturb the operation of the sensitive loads
- g) Disturbances in the communication networks and telephone lines
- h) Resonance between the supply inductance and capacitance of the power factor correction capacitors.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

There are two ways to analyse the time-varying harmonics in power systems. The first way is the estimation techniques, which are concerned with extracting useful information from the signal, such as amplitude, phase and frequency. Another way to analyse time-varying signals is using the concept of decomposition. Decomposition techniques are concerned with the way that the original signal can be split in individual components, including harmonics, inter harmonics, sub-harmonics, etc.

A. Historical Background

The decomposition provides a new way to harmonic analysis, because the signal decomposition is carried out in the time domain, allowing a better observation of the time-varying nature of the signals. This is an important issue in power quality analysis and the reason to focus on the harmonic decomposition techniques instead of estimation techniques. Few methods to decompose signals are as follows:-

1. SWRDFT Method :- SWRDFT method stands for “Sliding Window Recursive Discrete Fourier Transform” method. This method uses filter with imaginary co-efficients and construction of efficient band pass filter is not possible to minimize frequency spill over.
2. Adaptive Notch Filter Method :- This method uses second order notch filter and a non-linear differential equation for frequency update. This method is only applicable when few harmonics are present.
3. PLL Method :- PLL method for “Phase Locked Loop” method. It combines the use of analysis filter bank followed by a PLL estimator. This method is only applicable when few harmonics are present.

Fig. 2.1 – Previous filter bank to decompose the input signal in its harmonic components.

B. Conclusion

As the system shown in the figure has a problem in their development; the difficulty in the design of each band pass filter. The improvement is the establishment of multi rate technique using down - samplers and up - samplers.

III. MEASUREMENT OF HARMONICS DISTORTION

In this section, we will measure the harmonics voltage present in the utility supply. In order to measure the voltage of individual harmonics, it is important to know distortion due to harmonics present in the utility supply.

A. Extraction of Fundamental Frequency

In order to measure the total harmonics present in utility supply, we will use passive low pass filter. This filter will extract 50Hz fundamental frequency and will eliminate all the harmonics present in the power supply. The reason behind using passive low pass filter is as follows:-

1. They can handle large voltage, currents and powers.
2. There is no limitation on the frequency range.
3. They do not need Additional dc Power Supply for their operation.

In this filter,

V_{in} (Input Voltage) = Normal Power Supply

V_o (Output Voltage) = Fundamental Voltage (Voltage at 50 Hz)

V_{rms} = Input Fundamental Voltage present in Power Supply

V_d (Distortion Voltage) = Total Distortion present in Supply.

Fig. 3.1 – Passive low pass filter to extract fundamental frequency

Calculation :-

Let $R = 1K\Omega$, Cut-off Frequency (f_c) = 50 Hz

Then, $C = 1/2\pi Rf = 20\mu F$

$$\text{Capacitive Reactance } (X_c) = \frac{1}{2\pi C f} = 159.235 \Omega$$

$$\text{Impedance } (Z) = \sqrt{R^2 + X_c^2} = 1012.6 \Omega$$

$$\text{So, } V_o = V_{in} * (X_c / Z) = 35.7 \text{ V}$$

$$V_{rms} = V_o / G(j100\pi) \quad \text{where } G(j\omega) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \omega^2 C^2 R^2}}$$

$$= (35.7 / 0.157) = 227.38 \text{ V}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } V_d = \sqrt{V_{in}^2 - V_{rms}^2}$$

From experimental observations :-

For utility supply,

V_{in}	V_o	V_{rms}	V_d
233.5 V	35.7 V	227.38 V	53.109 V

For generator supply,

V_{in}	V_o	V_{rms}	V_d
247.48 V	35.35 V	225.193 V	102.63 V

From the above table, we can conclude that the total harmonics voltage (Sum of voltage of all the harmonics) is 53.109 V(for utility supply) and is 102.63 V(for generator supply)

B. Extraction of Third Harmonic using Passive Filter

For this we have to use a filter circuit which is cascade together of a low pass filter circuit with a high pass filter circuit, so that we can produce another type of passive RC filter that passes a selected range or “band” of frequency that can either narrow or wide while attenuating all those outside of this range.

So, circuit is :

Band Pass Filter

Fig. 4.1 – Passive band pass filter to extract third harmonic

So the transfer function is :

$$\frac{V_o(s)}{V_i(s)} = \frac{1}{\left(sC + \frac{1}{R} + \frac{1}{R + \frac{1}{sC}} \right)} * \frac{sC}{(1 + sCR)}$$

$$= \frac{sCR}{s^2C^2R^2 + 1 + 3sCR} \quad \text{where } f_0 = 1 / (2\pi RC)$$

Putting $s = j\omega$ and $\omega_0 = 2\pi f_0$ therefore the equation becomes :

$$\text{Gain} = |H_{BP}(j\omega)| = \left| \frac{V_o}{V_i} \right| = \frac{1/3}{\sqrt{1 + Q^2 \left(\frac{f}{f_0} - \frac{f_0}{f} \right)^2}}$$

Where $Q = 1/3$

While designing passive bandpass filter for 150 Hz, we found here that gain at 50 Hz is less than gain at 150 Hz. Since, 50 Hz voltage is much higher than 150 Hz voltage which makes 50 Hz much more dominant over 150 Hz.

f(Hz)	Gain
50	0.2466
150	0.33
250	0.176
350	0.1322

Thus, from the above table it is quite clear that passive filter cannot be used to extract harmonics from utility supply.

Before proceeding to active filter, it is necessary to note the quality factor (Q) needed for designing of active filter. Thus, from above equation we can find the accurate value of quality factor.

Gain at 50 Hz:

$$|G(50Hz)| = \frac{1/3}{\sqrt{1 + Q^2(8/3)^2}}$$

Q	G(j100π)	V ₁ (rms value of the fundamental component in the output of the filter)
10	0.0118	2.65 V
100	0.001289	0.265 V
250	0.00048	0.106 V

Thus, from the above table it is quite clear that in order to attenuate fundamental frequency for extraction of harmonic from utility supply through active filter minimum value of quality factor should be at least 250.

C. Extraction of Third Harmonic using Active Filter

As discussed in previous section, the design of circuit using active filter for extraction of third harmonic is only possible iff quality factor should be more than 250 so that the fundamental frequency should be attenuated as much as possible. In this section, we will measure the third harmonics voltage present in the utility supply using active filter with quality factor at least 250.

1. Feedback filter to extract third harmonic:

Multiple –Feedback filters utilize more than feedback path. Unlike their KRC counter parts which configure the op amp for a finite gain K, multiple feedback filters exploits the full open loop gain and are also referred as infinite gain filters. Together with KRC filter these are the most popular single op amp realization of second order responses.

Fig. 5.1 – Multiple Feedback band pass filter to extract third harmonic

$$BW = f_0/Q \quad \text{where } Q = 250$$

$$= 150/250 = 0.6$$

Let $C_1=C_2=C$ and $A_{max} = 1$ (for 150 Hz)

$$\omega_0 = 2\pi f_0 = 2\pi * 150 = 942.48$$

$$R_1 = \frac{Q}{A_{max}\omega_0 C} = \frac{0.265}{C} \Omega$$

$$R_2 = \frac{2Q}{\omega_0 C} = \frac{0.53}{C} \Omega$$

$$R_3 = \frac{Q}{\omega_0 C(2Q^2 - A_{max})} = \frac{0.265}{C * 124999} \Omega$$

The different values of resistances is tabulated assuming different values of capacitor :-

C (assume)	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃
1mF	265 Ω	530 Ω	2.12 mΩ
1μF	265 KΩ	530 KΩ	2.12 Ω
1nF	265 MΩ	530 MΩ	2.12 KΩ

We can't use very large value of resistors because the air around resistor become ionized and due to this several parallel virtual resistor comes along this large resistor which finally the resultant resistance become low.

We can't use low value resistance because the resistance due to this contacts will come in series with it which will have significant value and can't be ignored.

2. KRC filter to extract third harmonic:

This circuit consist of RC stage followed by CR stage to synthesize a band pass block, a gain block to provide positive feedback via R₃. This feedback is designed to bolster the response near $\omega / \omega_0 = 1$. the ac analysis of filter yields $V_o / V_i = H_{OBP} * H_{BP}$ where

$$|H_{BP}(j\omega)| = \frac{\frac{\omega}{Q\omega_0}}{\sqrt{\left\{1 - \left(\frac{\omega}{\omega_0}\right)^2\right\}^2 + \left(\frac{\omega}{Q\omega_0}\right)^2}}$$

Let $R_A = 5 \text{ K}\Omega$ and $C_1 = C_2 = C = 8 \mu\text{F}$

$$\text{From, } \omega_0 = \frac{\sqrt{1 + \frac{R_1}{R_3}}}{\sqrt{R_1 C_1 R_2 C_2}}$$

We got the value of $R_1 = 87.88 \text{ K}\Omega$ and $R_2 = R_3 = 129.5 \Omega$

Here, $Q = 250$ and $\omega_0 = 2\pi f_0 = 2\pi * 150 = 942.48$

Fig. 5.2 – Sallen Key band pass filter to extract third harmonic

$$\text{Since, } Q = \frac{\sqrt{1 + \frac{R_1}{R_3}}}{\left[1 + (1-K) \frac{R_1}{R_3} \right] \sqrt{\frac{R_2 C_2}{R_1 C_1}} + \sqrt{\frac{R_1 C_2}{R_2 C_1}} + \sqrt{\frac{R_1 C_1}{R_2 C_2}}}$$

Then, $K = 2.95$

Thus, $R_B = (K-1) \cdot R_A = 10 \text{ K}\Omega$

The gain of filter is given by the following equation :-

$$|H_{OBP} \cdot H_{BP}(j\omega)| = \frac{K}{1 + (1-K) \frac{R_1}{R_3} + (1 + \frac{C_1}{C_2}) \frac{R_1}{R_2}} * \frac{\frac{\omega}{Q\omega_0}}{\sqrt{\left\{ 1 - \left(\frac{\omega}{\omega_0}\right)^2 \right\}^2 + \left(\frac{\omega}{Q\omega_0}\right)^2}}$$

The frequency response of above filter is as follows:-

Fig. 5.3 – Frequency Response of Sallen Key band pass filter

Therefore, the gain offered by filter at different frequencies is tabulated as follows :-

f(Hz)	Gain
50	0.0016
150	0.07
250	0.0015

The response of above filter is as follows:-

Fig. 5.4 – Response of Sallen Key band pass

From the above observation, it is quite clear that filter to extract third harmonic is not possible through multiple – feedback filter. But, it is possible to extract third harmonic through KRC filter. The problem of gain can be solved by using an amplifier of suitable gain.

D. Extraction of fifth harmonic

As discussed in previous section, the design of circuit using active filter for extraction of third harmonic is possible through KRC filter. In this section, we will measure the fifth harmonics voltage present in the utility supply using active filter.

1. Feedback filter to extract fifth harmonic:

The circuit diagram for extraction of fifth harmonic is as follows:-

Fig. 6.1 – Multiple Feedback band pass filter to extract fifth harmonic

$$BW = f_0/Q \quad \text{where } Q = 250$$

$$= 250/250 = 1$$

Let $C_1=C_2=C$ and $A_{max} = 1$ (for 250 Hz)

$$\omega_0 = 2\pi f_0 = 2\pi * 250 = 1570.79$$

$$R_1 = \frac{Q}{A_{max}\omega_0 C}$$

$$= \frac{0.1591}{C} \Omega$$

$$R_2 = \frac{2Q}{\omega_0 C}$$

$$= \frac{0.3183}{C} \Omega$$

$$R_3 = \frac{Q}{\omega_0 C(2Q^2 - A_{max})}$$

$$= \frac{0.1591}{C * 124999} \Omega$$

The different values of resistances is tabulated assuming different values of capacitor:-

C (assume)	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃
1mF	159.1 Ω	318.3 Ω	1.27 mΩ
1μF	159.1 KΩ	318.3 KΩ	1.27 Ω
1nF	159.1 MΩ	318.3 MΩ	1.27 KΩ

From the above table, we found that extraction of fifth harmonic from multiple – feedback filter is not possible due to the reasons mentioned in section 5.2

2. KRC filter to extract fifth harmonic:

As we know that voltage of fifth harmonic is very much low as compared to voltages of fundamental frequency(50 Hz) and third harmonic(150 Hz). So, it is quite difficult to extract the fifth harmonic from the utility supply without attenuating fundamental frequency and third harmonic as very small amount of gain will generate a high voltage as compared to voltage of fifth harmonic. The attenuation of above two frequencies can be done using notch filter but using of notch filter will cause loading effect which will make the construction of filter much more complex.

Thus, from the above observation it is quite clear that extraction of harmonics is not possible through active filters. So, in order to extract the harmonics we need to use digital filters.

IV. MEASUREMENT OF HARMONICS DISTORTION - II

A. Extraction of Fundamental using low pass IIR digital filter

In this section, we will extract the fundamental present in the utility supply using low pass IIR digital filter.

A first-order casual lowpass IIR digital filter has a transfer function given by

$$H_{LP}(z) = \frac{1 - \alpha}{2} \left(\frac{1 + z^{-1}}{1 - \alpha z^{-1}} \right)$$

where $|\alpha| < 1$ for stability.

$$\text{And, } |H_{LP}(e^{j\theta})| = 1 ; |H_{LP}(e^{j\pi})| = 0$$

Now,

$$\cos \omega_c = \frac{2\alpha}{1+\alpha^2} ; \alpha = \frac{1-\sin \omega_c}{\cos \omega_c}$$

$$\text{Here } \omega_c = \frac{2*\pi*f}{f_c} ; f_c = 50\text{Hz} \ \& \ f = 50\text{Hz}$$

$$\text{So } \omega_c = \frac{2*\pi*50}{50} = 6.28$$

$$\text{And } \alpha = \frac{1-\sin 6.28}{\cos 6.28} = 0.89$$

It follows from

$$\begin{aligned} |H_{LP}(e^{j\omega})| &= \frac{\{(1-\alpha)*\cos\frac{\omega}{2}\}}{\sqrt{1+\alpha^2-2\alpha \cos \omega}} \\ &= \frac{\{(1-0.89)*\cos\frac{\omega}{2}\}}{\sqrt{1+0.89^2-2*0.89*\cos \omega}} \end{aligned}$$

Above equation is shown in simulink as follow

Fig 7.1: Representation of magnitude function of low pass IIR digital filter in Simulink

Fig 7.2: Frequency response of low pass IIR digital filter

Now filter for measuring fundamental by using Low-pass IIR digital filter as shown below. The cascade of four equivalent filter is taken because of increase the order of overall filter.

Fig 7.3: Low pass IIR digital filter for measuring fundamental

In the above filter diagram,

$$\text{Input} = 300 \sin(100\pi t) + 50 \sin(300\pi t)$$

Sample time in zero order hold circuit = $\{1/(128*50)\}$, and sample time in other blocks is -1.

$$\text{Value in gain block} = \frac{(1-0.89)^4}{2^4}$$

Thus the response of above filter is shown below

Fig 7.4: Response of low pass IIR digital filter

From the above response, following observations are recorded for fundamental

Input magnitude	Output magnitude	Input frequency	Output frequency	Gain
300V	214V	50Hz	50Hz	0.7133

So, we found that this filter is not suitable for extraction of fundamental as the overall gain of the filter is lower than the required gain.

B. Extraction of Fundamental using band pass IIR digital filter

A 2nd-order band-pass IIR digital filter has a transfer function given by

$$H_{BP}(z) = \frac{1 - \alpha}{2} \left(\frac{1 - z^{-2}}{1 - \beta(1 + \alpha)z^{-1} + \alpha z^{-2}} \right)$$

where, centre frequency; $\omega_0 = \cos^{-1} \beta$

Bandwidth; $B_w = \omega_{c_2} - \omega_{c_1} = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{2\alpha}{1 + \alpha^2} \right)$

and $|\alpha| < 1$ & $|\beta| < 1$

here we have to take $\alpha = 0.99$

and $\omega_0 = \frac{2 * \pi * f}{f_c}$; where $f_c = 2^7 * 50\text{Hz}$ & $f = 50\text{Hz}$

So, $\omega_0 = \frac{2 * 180 * 50}{128 * 50} = 2.8125$

Hence, $\beta = \cos(\omega_0) = \cos(2.8125) = 0.9987$

Its magnitude function is

$$|H_{BP}(e^{j\omega})| = \frac{(1 - \alpha) * \sin(\omega)}{\sqrt{1 + \beta^2(1 + \alpha^2) + \alpha^2 - 2\beta(1 + \alpha^2) \cos(\omega) + 2\alpha \cos(2\omega)}}$$

$$= \frac{(1 - 0.99) * \sin(\omega)}{\sqrt{1 + 0.9987^2(1 + 0.99^2) + 0.99^2 - 2 * 0.9987 * (1 + 0.99^2) \cos(\omega) + 2 * 0.99 * \cos(2\omega)}}$$

Above equation is shown in simulink as follow

Power System Harmonic Extraction Using DSP Technique

Fig 8.1: Representation of magnitude function of band pass IIR digital filter for fundamental in simulink

Fig 8.2: Frequency response of Band pass IIR digital filter for fundamental

From the above response, following observations are recorded

Analog frequency (Hz)	Digital frequency (rad/sec)	Gain
50	0.049	0.93
150	0.147	0.0774
250	0.2453	0.0426

Now filter for extracting fundamental by using bandpass IIR digital filter as shown below. The cascade of two equivalent filter is taken because of increase the order of overall filter.

Fig 8.3: Band pass IIR digital filter for fundamental

In the above filter diagram,

$$\text{Input} = 300 \sin(100\pi t) + 50 \sin(300\pi t) + 10 \sin(500\pi t) + \sin(700\pi t) + 0.1 \sin(900\pi t)$$

Sample time in zero order hold circuit = $\{1/(128*50)\}$, and sample time in other blocks is -1.

$$\text{Value in gain block} = \frac{(1-0.99)^2}{2^2} * 1.15$$

Thus the response of above filter is shown below

Fig 8.4: Filter Response for fundamental

From the above response, following observations are recorded for fundamental

Input magnitude	Output magnitude	Input frequency	Output frequency	Gain
300V	300V	50Hz	50Hz	1

From above filter response we found that the overall gain of the filter is 1 and the time period of oscillation is 0.02. So the frequency will be 50Hz. Hence, it concluded that the fundamental frequency can be extracted successfully by this filter.

C. Extraction of Third Harmonic

A 2nd-order band-pass IIR digital filter has a transfer function given by

$$H_{BP}(z) = \frac{1 - \alpha}{2} \left(\frac{1 - z^{-2}}{1 - \beta(1 + \alpha)z^{-1} + \alpha z^{-2}} \right)$$

where, centre frequency; $\omega_0 = \cos^{-1} \beta$

Bandwidth; $B_w = \omega_{c_2} - \omega_{c_1} = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{2\alpha}{1 + \alpha^2} \right)$

and $|\alpha| < 1$ & $|\beta| < 1$

here we have to take $\alpha = 0.99$

and $\omega_0 = \frac{2 * \pi * f}{f_c}$; where $f_c = 2^7 * 50\text{Hz}$ & $f = 150\text{Hz}$

$$\text{So, } \omega_0 = \frac{2 * 180 * 150}{128 * 50} = 8.4375$$

Hence, $\beta = \cos(\omega_0) = \cos(8.4375) = 0.99$

Power System Harmonic Extraction Using DSP Technique

Its magnitude function is

$$|H_{BP}(e^{j\omega})| = \frac{(1 - \alpha) * \sin(\omega)}{\sqrt{1 + \beta^2(1 + \alpha^2) + \alpha^2 - 2\beta(1 + \alpha^2) \cos(\omega) + 2\alpha \cos(2\omega)}}$$

$$= \frac{(1-0.99)*\sin(\omega)}{\sqrt{1+0.99^2(1+0.99^2)+0.99^2-2*0.99*(1+0.99^2)\cos(\omega)+2*0.99*\cos(2\omega)}}$$

Above equation is shown in simulink as follow

Fig 8.5: Representation of magnitude function of band pass IIR digital filter for Third harmonic in simulink

And the frequency response of same equation from above simulink diagram is

Fig 8.6: Frequency Response of band pass IIR digital filter for third harmonic

From the above response, following observations are recorded

Analog frequency (Hz)	Digital frequency (rad/sec)	Gain
50	0.049	0.628
150	0.147	0.685
250	0.2453	0.062

Now filter for extracting third harmonic by using bandpass IIR digital filter as shown below. The cascade of two equivalent filter is taken because of increase the order of overall filter.

Fig 8.7: Band pass IIR digital filter for third harmonic

In above filter diagram,

$$\text{Input} = 300 \sin(100\pi t) + 50 \sin(300\pi t) + 10 \sin(500\pi t) + \sin(700\pi t) + 0.1 \sin(900\pi t)$$

Sample time in zero order hold circuit = $\{1/(128*50)\}$, and sample time in other blocks is - 1.

$$\text{Value in gain block} = \frac{(1-0.99)^2}{2^2} * 2.2148$$

Thus the response of above filter is shown below

Fig 8.8: Filter Response for third harmonic

From the above response, following observations are recorded for third harmonic

Input magnitude	Output magnitude	Input frequency	Output frequency	Gain
50V	50V	150Hz	150Hz	1

From above filter response we found that the overall gain of the filter is 1 and the time period of oscillation is 0.006666. So the frequency will be 150Hz. Hence, it concluded that the third harmonic can be extracted successfully by this filter.

D. Extraction of Fifth Harmonic

A 2nd-order band-pass IIR digital filter has a transfer function given by

$$H_{BP}(z) = \frac{1-\alpha}{2} \left(\frac{1-z^{-2}}{1-\beta(1+\alpha)z^{-1}+\alpha z^{-2}} \right)$$

where, centre frequency; $\omega_0 = \cos^{-1} \beta$

Bandwidth; $B_w = \omega_{c_2} - \omega_{c_1} = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{2\alpha}{1+\alpha^2} \right)$

and $|\alpha| < 1$ & $|\beta| < 1$

here we have to take $\alpha = 0.99$

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and $\omega_0 = \frac{2*\pi*f}{f_c}$; where $f_c = 2^7 * 50Hz$ & $f = 250Hz$

So, $\omega_0 = \frac{2*180*250}{128*50} = 14.0625$

Hence, $\beta = \cos(\omega_0) = \cos(14.0625) = 0.97$

Its magnitude function is

$$|H_{BP}(e^{j\omega})| = \frac{(1 - \alpha) * \sin(\omega)}{\sqrt{1 + \beta^2(1 + \alpha^2) + \alpha^2 - 2\beta(1 + \alpha^2) \cos(\omega) + 2\alpha \cos(2\omega)}}$$

$$= \frac{(1-0.99)*\sin(\omega)}{\sqrt{1+0.97^2(1+0.99^2)+0.99^2-2*0.97*(1+0.99^2) \cos(\omega)+2*0.99*\cos(2\omega)}}$$

Above equation is shown in simulink as follow

Fig 8.9: Representation of magnitude function of band pass IIR digital filter for fifth harmonic in simulink

And the frequency response of same equation from above simulink diagram is

Fig 8.10: Frequency Response of band pass IIR digital filter for fifth harmonic

From the above response, following observations are recorded

Analog frequency (Hz)	Digital frequency (rad/sec)	Gain
50	0.049	$8.55 * 10^{-3}$
150	0.147	0.03825
250	0.2453	0.9945

Now filter for extracting fifth harmonic by using bandpass IIR digital filter as shown below. The cascade of two equivalent filter is taken because of increase the order of overall filter.

Fig 8.11: Band pass IIR digital filter for fifth harmonic

In above filter diagram,

$$\text{Input} = 300 \sin(100\pi t) + 50 \sin(300\pi t) + 10 \sin(500\pi t) + \sin(700\pi t) + 0.1 \sin(900\pi t)$$

Sample time in zero order hold circuit = $\{1/(128*50)\}$, and sample time in other blocks is -1.

$$\text{Value in gain block} = \frac{(1-0.99)^2}{2^2}$$

Thus the response of above filter is shown below

Fig 8.12: Filter Response for fifth harmonic

From the above response, following observations are recorded for fifth harmonic

Input magnitude	Output magnitude	Input frequency	Output frequency	Gain
10V	10V	250Hz	250Hz	1

From above filter response we found that the overall gain of the filter is 1 and the time period of oscillation is 0.004. So the frequency will be 250Hz. Hence, it concluded that the fifth harmonic can be extracted successfully by this filter.

E. Extraction of Seventh Harmonic

A 2nd-order band-pass IIR digital filter has a transfer function given by

$$H_{BP}(z) = \frac{1 - \alpha}{2} \left(\frac{1 - z^{-2}}{1 - \beta(1 + \alpha)z^{-1} + \alpha z^{-2}} \right)$$

where, centre frequency; $\omega_0 = \cos^{-1} \beta$

Bandwidth; $B_w = \omega_{c_2} - \omega_{c_1} = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{2\alpha}{1 + \alpha^2} \right)$

and $|\alpha| < 1$ & $|\beta| < 1$

here we have to take $\alpha = 0.99$

and $\omega_0 = \frac{2*\pi*f}{f_c}$; where $f_c = 2^7 * 50Hz$ & $f = 350Hz$

So, $\omega_0 = \frac{2*180*350}{128*50} = 19.6875$

Hence, $\beta = \cos(\omega_0) = \cos(19.6875) = 0.941$

Its magnitude function is

$$|H_{BP}(e^{j\omega})| = \frac{(1 - \alpha) * \sin(\omega)}{\sqrt{1 + \beta^2(1 + \alpha^2) + \alpha^2 - 2\beta(1 + \alpha^2) \cos(\omega) + 2\alpha \cos(2\omega)}}$$

$$= \frac{(1-0.99)*\sin(\omega)}{\sqrt{1+0.941^2(1+0.99^2)+0.99^2-2*0.941*(1+0.99^2)\cos(\omega)+2*0.99*\cos(2\omega)}}$$

Above equation is shown in simulink as follow

Fig 8.13: Representation of magnitude function of band pass IIR digital filter for seventh harmonic in Simulink

And the frequency response of same equation from above simulink diagram is

Fig 8.14: Frequency Response of band pass IIR digital filter for seventh harmonic

From the above response, following observations are recorded

Analog frequency (Hz)	Digital frequency (rad/sec)	Gain
50	0.049	$4.25 * 10^{-3}$
150	0.147	0.0154
250	0.2453	0.04268
350	0.3434	0.998

Now filter for extracting seventh harmonic by using bandpass IIR digital filter as shown below. The cascade of two equivalent filter is taken because of increase the order of overall filter.

Fig 8.15: Band pass IIR digital filter for seventh harmonic

In above filter diagram,

$$\text{Input} = 300 \sin(100\pi t) + 50 \sin(300\pi t) + 10 \sin(500\pi t) + \sin(700\pi t) + 0.1 \sin(900\pi t)$$

Sample time in zero order hold circuit = $\{1/(128*50)\}$, and sample time in other blocks is - 1.

$$\text{Value in gain block} = \frac{(1-0.99)^2}{2^2}$$

Thus the response of above filter is shown below

Fig 8.16: Filter Response for seventh harmonic

From the above response, following observations are recorded for seventh harmonic

Input magnitude	Output magnitude	Input frequency	Output frequency	Gain
1 V	1 V	350 Hz	350 Hz	1

From above filter response we found that the overall gain of the filter is 1 and the time period of oscillation is 0.0028571. So the frequency will be 350Hz. Hence, it concluded that the seventh harmonic can be extracted successfully by this filter.

F. Extraction of Ninth Harmonic

A 2nd-order band-pass IIR digital filter has a transfer function given by

$$H_{BP}(z) = \frac{1-\alpha}{2} \left(\frac{1-z^{-2}}{1-\beta(1+\alpha)z^{-1}+\alpha z^{-2}} \right)$$

where, centre frequency; $\omega_0 = \cos^{-1} \beta$

Bandwidth; $B_w = \omega_{c2} - \omega_{c1} = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{2\alpha}{1+\alpha^2} \right)$

and $|\alpha| < 1$ & $|\beta| < 1$

here we have to take $\alpha = 0.99$

and $\omega_0 = \frac{2*\pi*f}{f_c}$; where $f_c = 2^7 * 50\text{Hz}$ & $f = 450\text{Hz}$

Power System Harmonic Extraction Using DSP Technique

$$\text{So, } \omega_0 = \frac{2 \cdot 180 \cdot 450}{128 \cdot 50} = 25.3125$$

$$\text{Hence, } \beta = \cos(\omega_0) = \cos(25.3125) = 0.9039$$

Its magnitude function is

$$|H_{BP}(e^{j\omega})| = \frac{(1 - \alpha) * \sin(\omega)}{\sqrt{1 + \beta^2(1 + \alpha^2) + \alpha^2 - 2\beta(1 + \alpha^2) \cos(\omega) + 2\alpha \cos(2\omega)}}$$

$$= \frac{(1 - 0.99) * \sin(\omega)}{\sqrt{1 + 0.9039^2(1 + 0.99^2) + 0.99^2 - 2 * 0.9039 * (1 + 0.99^2) \cos(\omega) + 2 * 0.99 * \cos(2\omega)}}$$

Above equation is shown in simulink as follow

Fig 8.17: Representation of magnitude function of band pass IIR digital filter for ninth harmonic in simulink

And the frequency response of same equation from above simulink diagram is

Fig 8.18: Frequency Response of band pass IIR digital filter for ninth harmonic

From the above response, following observations are recorded

Analog frequency (Hz)	Digital frequency (rad/sec)	Gain
50	0.049	2.6×10^{-3}
150	0.147	8.6×10^{-3}
250	0.2453	0.0184
350	0.3434	0.0448
450	0.4415	0.9918

Now filter for extracting ninth harmonic by using bandpass IIR digital filter as shown below. The cascade of two equivalent filter is taken because of increase the order of overall filter.

Fig 8.19: Band pass IIR digital filter for ninth harmonic

In above filter diagram,

$$\text{Input} = 300 \sin(100\pi t) + 50 \sin(300\pi t) + 10 \sin(500\pi t) + \sin(700\pi t) + 0.1 \sin(900\pi t)$$

Sample time in zero order hold circuit = $\{1/(128 \times 50)\}$, and sample time in other blocks is -1.

$$\text{Value in gain block} = \frac{(1-0.99)^2}{2^2}$$

Thus the response of above filter is shown below

Fig 8.20: Filter Response for ninth harmonic

From the above response, following observations are recorded for ninth harmonic

Input magnitude	Output magnitude	Input frequency	Output frequency	Gain
1V	1V	350Hz	350Hz	1

From above filter response we found that the overall gain of the filter is 1 and the time period of oscillation is 0.0028571. So the frequency will be 350Hz. Hence, it concluded that the ninth harmonic can be extracted successfully by this filter.

From above all filters design and responses it is concluded that the fundamental and all odd harmonics of utility power supply can be extracted successfully by designing different IIR band pass digital filter according to the frequency required.

G. Extraction of DC Component from utility supply using low pass IIR digital filter

Sometime a DC component is also present in utility power supply due to any fault or other thing. In this section, we are extracting DC component from utility power supply by using low-pass IIR digital filter.

A first-order casual lowpass IIR digital filter has a transfer function given by

$$H_{LP}(z) = \frac{1 - \alpha}{2} \left(\frac{1 + z^{-1}}{1 - \alpha z^{-1}} \right)$$

where $|\alpha| < 1$ for stability.

And , $|H_{LP}(e^{j\theta})| = 1$; $|H_{LP}(e^{j\pi})| = 0$

Now,

$$\cos \omega_c = \frac{2\alpha}{1+\alpha^2} \quad ; \quad \alpha = \frac{1-\sin \omega_c}{\cos \omega_c}$$

Here $\omega_c = 0.1$

$$\cos(0.1) = \frac{2\alpha}{1+\alpha^2} = 0.999998476$$

$$\Rightarrow 0.999998476(1 + \alpha^2) - 2\alpha = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow \alpha = 0.99825$$

Now the filter for extracting DC component by using low-pass IIR digital filter as shown below. The cascade of three equivalent filter is taken because of increasing the order of overall filter.

Fig 9.1: Low pass IIR digital filter for DC

In above filter diagram,

Input = $10+300 \sin(100\pi t)$

Sample time in zero order hold circuit = $\{1/(128*50)\}$, and sample time in other blocks is -1.

Value in gain block = $\frac{(1-0.99825)^3}{2^3}$

Thus the response of above filter is shown below

Fig 9.2: Filter Response for DC

From the above response, following observations are recorded for fundamental

Input(volt)	Output(volt)
10	10

From above filter response it is concluded that the DC component can be extracted successfully by this filter.

V. EXTRACTION OF POWER SYSTEM HARMONICS BY FILTER BANK

In this section we will construct a filter bank for extraction of power system harmonics by using filters designed in previous section.

The overall construction of filter bank is done in Simulink so firstly we take a filter bank as a system. After that all the filters designed in previous section are taken in a subsystem of that system or filter bank. Inside the filter bank all the subsystem are assembled.

The filter bank with power utility supply in simulink as shown below:-

Fig 10.1: Filter Bank in simulink

Utility power supply is taken as an another system inside which the utility power supply given as

$$y(t) = 10 + 300\sin(100\pi t) + 50\sin(300\pi t) + 10\sin(500\pi t) + \sin(700\pi t) + 0.1\sin(900\pi t)$$

Inside power utility supply in above simulink diagram the power utility supply is shown as below

Fig 10.2: Subsystem for Power utility supply

The arrangement of subsystem inside the filter bank system also as shown below

Fig 10.3: Array of filter in Filter bank system

The filters inside each subsystem of above simulink diagram for DC, fundamental, and each harmonics with its respective responses are as shown below

For DC,

And its response:

For fundamental,

Response:

For 3rd harmonic,

Response:

For 5th harmonic,

Response:

For 7th harmonic,

Response:

For 9th harmonic

Response:

Digital filter bank is constructed successfully and it is possible to extract any harmonic component present in utility power supply with fundamental and DC component.

VI. VISUALIZING POWER SYSTEM HARMONICS BY DFT FILTER

In this section we are visualizing power system harmonics by using DFT filter.

For evaluating the DFT coefficients

$$X(k) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x(n) e^{-j\frac{2\pi}{N}nk}$$

N-point DFT of the sequence

1. $x(n) = 1 ; 0 \leq n \leq N-1$

$$X(K) = \begin{cases} N, & k = 0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

2. $x(n) = \cos(n\omega_0); 0 \leq n \leq N-1$

$$X(K) = \begin{cases} \frac{N}{2}, & k = k_0 \text{ and } k = N - k_0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

3. $x(n) = \sin(n\omega_0); 0 \leq n \leq N-1$

$$X(K) = \begin{cases} \frac{N}{j2}, & k = k_0 \\ -\frac{N}{j2}, & k = N - k_0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

4. $x(n) = 1 + \sin(n\omega_0) + \cos(n\omega_0) ; 0 \leq n \leq N-1$

$$X(K) = \begin{cases} N, & k = 0 \\ \frac{N}{2} + \frac{N}{j2}, & k = k_0 \\ \frac{N}{2} - \frac{N}{j2}, & k = N - k_0 \\ 0, & otherwise \end{cases}$$

Now, Let if we have a power utility supply as

$$x(t) = 5 + 300\{\sin(100\pi t) + \cos(100\pi t)\} + 50\{\sin(300\pi t) + \cos(300\pi t)\} + 10\{\sin(500\pi t) + \cos(500\pi t)\} + \{\sin(700\pi t) + \cos(700\pi t)\} + 0.1\{\sin(900\pi t) + \cos(900\pi t)\}; 0 \leq n \leq N-1$$

Experimental analysis in simulink is given below

Fig 11.1: DFT filter for visualizing power system harmonic

In above simulink diagram,

Value in Gain block = 1/80

Sample time in zero order hold block = 1/(16*50)

Output buffer size in buffer = 16

Response of above simulink diagram as shown below

1. Response of real part of DFT of given sequence

Fig 11.2: Filter response for real part of DFT

2. Response of imaginary part of DFT of given sequence

Fig 11.3: Filter response for imaginary part of DFT

Mathematical analysis of given sequence is tabulated as below

For gain = 1/80,

16 Point DFT coefficients	Estimated value
$X(0) = 1, X(1) = 30+30/j, X(2) = 5+5/j,$	$A_0 = 1, A_1 = 30, A_2 = 5, A_3 = 1,$
$X(3) = 1+1/j, X(4) = 0.1+0.1/j,$	$A_4 = 0.1, A_5 = 0.01$
$X(5) = 0.01+0.01/j, X(6), \dots, X(10) = 0,$	$B_1 = -j30, B_2 = -j5, B_3 = -j,$
$X(11) = 0.01-0.01/j, X(12) = 0.1-0.1/j$	$B_4 = -0.1j, B_5 = -0.01j$
$X(13) = 1-1/j, X(14) = 5-5/j, X(15) = 30-30/j$	

VII. CONCLUSION

1. It presents a new filter bank structure for time varying harmonic decomposition and is able to extract each harmonic in time domain.
2. Each filter of the bank has frequency centered at odd harmonic, but these band-pass filters have poor rejection for the even harmonics. Because this the energy of these components could leak into the adjacent odd harmonics.
3. The limitation of the methodology is associated with the real-time implementation, because the high computational effort and the long transient response of the filter bank.
4. The first problem can be deal with the use of high performance DSP processor, and the second problem is under investigation. However the method is well suitable for off-line analysis.

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